

Supporting Information: Global Sensitivity Analysis Using Polynomial Chaos Expansion on the Grassmann Manifold

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A Related Work Supplement: DMaps and GDMaps

The example¹ pertains to a set of 3,000 points, denoted as $S_N = \{\mathbf{X}_i\}_{i=1}^N$, which define cone-shaped structures in three-dimensional Euclidean space. The performance of the conventional diffusion maps (DMaps) and Grassmannian diffusion maps (GDMaps) are illustrated in Figs. A.1 to A.3.

Fig. A.1 shows the diffusion coordinates θ_i for both conventional DMaps and GDMaps, with the first and second diffusion coordinates determining the respective colour maps. When plotting θ_1 against θ_2 for GDMaps, a ring-like structure is observed, whereas a sail-like structure emerges when plotting θ_1 against θ_2 for conventional GDMaps.

Fig. A.1. 2D plots of the first two non-trivial diffusion coordinates from (a, b) DMaps and (c, d) GDMaps with a colour map defined by θ_1 (left column) and θ_2 (right column).

From Figs. A.2a and A.2b, when mapped in the ambient space \mathbb{R}^3 , conventional DMaps exhibit a logical order according to the canonical directions. However, as shown in Fig. A.2c, the same diffusion coordinates look scrambled and lack a logical parameterisation when they are mapped on the Grassmann manifold. This highlights that while conventional DMaps can discover a low-dimensional structure in

¹ As discussed in the main document, this example was previously used by Dos Santos et al. [3].

Fig. A.2. Conventional DMaps on the collection of points S_N defining two cone-like structures \mathbb{R}^3 : (a) the first and (b) the second diffusion coordinates mapped in the ambient space \mathbb{R}^3 ; (c) the first and (d) the second diffusion coordinates mapped on the Grassmann manifold $\mathcal{G}(1,3)$.

Fig. A.3. GDMaps on the collection of points S_N defining two cone-like structures \mathbb{R}^3 : (a) the first and (b) the second diffusion coordinates mapped in the ambient space \mathbb{R}^3 ; (c) the first and (d) the second diffusion coordinates mapped on the Grassmann manifold $\mathcal{G}(1,3)$.

the ambient space, it fails to capture the intrinsic subspace structure of the data adequately. When compared to GDMaps, the first and second diffusion coordinates in \mathbb{R}^3 in Figs. A.3a and A.3b and

on the Grassmannian in Figs. A.3c and A.3d are organised in a way that closely resembles the data's intrinsic subspace structure.

B Methods Supplement

B.1 GSA Using Grassmannian Diffusion Maps and PCE

Grassmannian Diffusion Maps The GDMaps method is a two-stage dimensionality reduction technique involving linear pointwise and non-linear multipoint dimension reduction. We start with an ensemble of \mathcal{N} independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) samples drawn from a joint probability density function (PDF) $f_{\mathbf{X}}$ comprising experimental design (ED) $\mathcal{X} = \{\mathbf{X}_i \in \mathbb{R}^k\}_{i=1}^{\mathcal{N}}$ and \mathcal{N} high-dimensional output data produced by a model (e.g., an agent-based model (ABM)) $\mathcal{Y} = \{\mathcal{M}(\mathbf{X}_i)\}_{i=1}^{\mathcal{N}} = \{\mathbf{Y}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}\}_{i=1}^{\mathcal{N}}$.

The first step is to project each point \mathbf{Y}_i onto a Grassmann manifold, assuming that \mathbf{Y}_i has a low-rank structure. Grassmann manifold or Grassmannian denoted as $\mathcal{G}(p, n)$, and defined as a set of p -dimensional subspaces (or p -planes) embedded in n -dimensional Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^n . The projection is performed via singular value decomposition (SVD) for each point \mathbf{Y}_i into three matrices: $\mathbf{Y}_i = \mathbf{U}_i \mathbf{\Sigma}_i \mathbf{V}_i^T$, where $\mathbf{\Sigma}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times p}$ is a diagonal matrix containing singular values. $\mathbf{U}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times p}$ and $\mathbf{V}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times p}$ are orthonormal matrices; hence, we consider them to reside on the Grassmannian manifolds: $\mathcal{G}(p, n) = \{\text{span}(\mathbf{U}) : \mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times p}\}$ and $\mathcal{G}(p, m) = \{\text{span}(\mathbf{V}) : \mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times p}\}$, respectively. The number of p -planes defining the Grassmann manifold $\mathcal{G}(n, p)$ is an important hyper-parameter determining the ranks of \mathbf{U}_i and \mathbf{V}_i , and thus the accuracy level of data representation on the Grassmannian, which was found to significantly affect the predictive ability of a surrogate constructed at a later stage [5]. The Grassmannian dimension p can be specified a priori, e.g., as a maximum or minimum rank of all input matrices \mathbf{Y}_i . Practically speaking, we use SVD to identify a basis for each \mathbf{Y}_i , and the resulting space spanned by this basis is a point on the Grassmannian representing the projection of the data onto the manifold. \mathbf{U}_i and \mathbf{V}_i represent the dimension-reduced data on which we later operate.

We begin the non-linear dimensionality reduction step by considering a positive semi-definite Grassmannian kernel defined as a map $k : \mathcal{G}(p, n) \times \mathcal{G}(p, n) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and construct the kernel matrices $[k(\mathbf{U}_i, \mathbf{U}_j)] \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{N}}$ and $[k(\mathbf{V}_i, \mathbf{V}_j)] \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{N}}$. In this work, we use the projection kernel defined as

$$k_{pr}(\mathbf{U}_i, \mathbf{U}_j) = \|\mathbf{U}_i^T \mathbf{U}_j\|_F^2. \quad (1)$$

For further information about other Grassmannian kernels, their construction and application, we refer the reader to Dos Santos et al. [3]. Using the constructed kernels, we compile the composed kernel matrix $K(\mathbf{U}, \mathbf{V})$ by taking the Hadamard product of the corresponding kernels: $K(\mathbf{U}, \mathbf{V}) = K(\mathbf{U}) \circ K(\mathbf{V})$. Alternatively, one can create the composed kernel matrix by summing $K(\mathbf{U}) + K(\mathbf{V})$.

The composed kernel matrix is used to define a random walk with a probability distribution f , and the transition probability matrix \mathbf{P} over the data on the Grassmann manifold $\mathcal{G}(p, n)$, given by sets $\mathcal{U} = \{\mathcal{U}_i\}_{i=1}^{\mathcal{N}}$ and $\mathcal{V} = \{\mathcal{V}_i\}_{i=1}^{\mathcal{N}}$, where $\mathcal{U}_i = \text{span}(\mathbf{U}_i)$ and $\mathcal{V}_i = \text{span}(\mathbf{V}_i)$, respectively, denoted as $W = (\{\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{V}\}, f, \mathbf{P})$. The transition probability matrix $\mathbf{P} = [P_{ij}]$ of the random walk W over the Grassmannian is built as follows. First, the diagonal degree matrix $\mathbf{D} \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{N}}$ is constructed as $D_{ii} = \sum_{j=1}^{\mathcal{N}} k_{ij}$, determining the stationary distribution of the random walk W as $\pi_i = D_{ii} / \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\mathcal{N}} D_{kk}\right)$. Next, we use the kernel matrix k_{ij} normalised as $\kappa_{ij} = k_{ij} / \sqrt{D_{ii} D_{jj}}$ to obtain the transition probability matrix $\mathbf{P} = [P_{ij}]$ given by

$$P_{ij} = \frac{k_{ij}}{\sum_{k=1}^{\mathcal{N}} \kappa_{ik}}. \quad (2)$$

Thus, we run the diffusion process on the manifold, and from the eigendecomposition of \mathbf{P} , we retain the first g eigenvectors $\{\psi_k\}_{k=1}^g$ with $\psi_k \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{N}}$ and their respective eigenvalues $\{\lambda_k\}_{k=1}^g$. The Grassmannian diffusion coordinates for every element $\mathbf{Y}_i \in \mathcal{Y}$ are given by

$$\Theta_i = (\theta_{i0}, \dots, \theta_{ig}) = (\lambda_0 \psi_{i0}, \dots, \lambda_g \psi_{ig}). \quad (3)$$

Given the decaying spectrum of eigenvalues $\{\lambda_0, \dots, \lambda_{\mathcal{N}}\}$ of the sparse Markov matrix, it is sufficient to keep small g diffusion coordinates to describe the essential geometric structure of the data [5].

Polynomial Chaos Expansion on the Grassmann Manifold polynomial chaos expansion (PCE) expresses the relationship between the input and output in terms of orthogonal polynomials chosen to be orthonormal with respect to PDF of the input random variables (RVs). Here, the input is defined as $\mathcal{X} = \{\mathbf{X}_i \in \mathbb{R}^k\}_{i=1}^{\mathcal{N}}$ with assumed independent components described by a joint probability distribution $f_{\mathbf{X}}$, and the output is diffusion coordinates, representing the low-dimensional manifold of the original data $\Theta = \{\Theta_i \in \mathbb{R}^g\}_{i=1}^{\mathcal{N}}$. Thus, we use a PCE surrogate model to approximate a mapping between input parameters and coordinates on the diffusion manifold $\mathcal{E} : \mathbf{X} \rightarrow \Theta$ as:

$$\tilde{\mathcal{E}}(\mathbf{X}) = \sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{T}} \eta_{\mathbf{s}} \Phi_{\mathbf{s}}(\mathbf{X}), \quad (4)$$

where $\Phi_{\mathbf{s}}(\mathbf{X}) = \prod_{i=1}^k \phi_{s_i}^{(i)}(X_i)$, assuming independence, are multivariate orthonormal polynomials with respect to $f_{\mathbf{X}}$ such that $\langle \Phi_{\mathbf{s}}(\mathbf{X}) \Phi_{\mathbf{t}}(\mathbf{X}) \rangle = \int_{\mathcal{Z}} \Phi_{\mathbf{s}}(\mathbf{X}) \Phi_{\mathbf{t}}(\mathbf{X}) f_{\mathbf{X}}(\mathbf{X}) d\mathbf{X} = \gamma_{\mathbf{s}} \delta_{\mathbf{s}\mathbf{t}}$; $\eta_{\mathbf{s}} \in \mathbb{R}^g$ are corresponding PCE coefficients that are vector-valued with dimension equal to the number of retained diffusion coordinates g . Multi-indices $\mathbf{s} = (s_1, \dots, s_k)$ are uniquely associated to the single indices s , and \mathcal{T} is a total-degree multi-index set satisfying $\|\mathbf{s}\|_1 \leq s_{\max}$, $s_{\max} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$, resulting in a PCE basis of size $\frac{(k+s_{\max})!}{k!s_{\max}!}$, which scales polynomially with the number of input dimensions k , and maximal polynomial degree s_{\max} .

With the fixed multi-index set \mathcal{T} , we get PCE coefficients $\eta_{\mathbf{s}}$, by solving the least square problem:

$$\arg \min_{\eta \in \mathbb{R}^{\#\mathcal{T}}} \frac{1}{\mathcal{N}} \sum_{i=1}^{\mathcal{N}} \left\{ \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{X}_i) - \sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{T}} \eta_{\mathbf{s}} \Phi_{\mathbf{s}}(\mathbf{X}_i) \right\}^2. \quad (5)$$

One can introduce a penalty term in the equation above to avoid overfitting and thus consider LASSO (Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator) or Ridge regression methods [7].

To approximate generalisation error, we use the validation error, as defined by Kontolati et al. [5]:

$$\epsilon_{\text{val}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{\mathcal{N}_*} \left(\Theta_i^* - \tilde{\mathcal{E}}(\mathbf{X}_i^*) \right)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^{\mathcal{N}_*} \left(\Theta_i^* - \bar{\Theta}^* \right)^2}, \quad (6)$$

where $\{\mathbf{X}_i^* \in \mathbb{R}^k\}_{i=1}^{\mathcal{N}_*}$ and $\{\Theta_i^* \in \mathbb{R}^g\}_{i=1}^{\mathcal{N}_*}$ constitute a test set, which we choose to be of size $\mathcal{N}_* = \frac{1}{3}\mathcal{N}$ and $\bar{\Theta}^* = \frac{1}{\mathcal{N}_*} \sum_{i=1}^{\mathcal{N}_*} \Theta_i^*$ is the mean response of the test set on the latent space.

Sobol' Indices Using Polynomial Chaos Expansion on the Grassmann Manifold Necessary components for calculating Sobol' indices include the total variance $D = \mathbb{V}[Y]$ and the partial variances of individual parameters and their interactions. Once the coefficients $\eta_{\mathbf{s}}$ in Eq. (4) have been determined, it becomes straightforward to obtain estimates for the Sobol' indices. That is, the approximation of the mean and variance of $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}(\mathbf{X})$ can be easily achieved using

$$\mathbb{E}[\tilde{\mathcal{E}}(\mathbf{X})] = \eta_{\mathbf{0}} \gamma_{\mathbf{0}}, \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbb{V}[\tilde{\mathcal{E}}(\mathbf{X})] = \sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{T}, \mathbf{s} \neq \mathbf{0}} \eta_{\mathbf{s}}^2 \gamma_{\mathbf{s}}. \quad (7)$$

Regarding the partial variances, we can interpret the PCE coefficients with the multi-index set \mathcal{T} as partial variances, provided that specific interactions are already determined by multi-indices \mathbf{s} . In particular, each multi-index $\mathbf{s} = (s_1, \dots, s_k)$ is uniquely characterised by single indices s , corresponding to each of the k random inputs. As a result, we can gather multi-indices related to partial variance caused by random inputs indexed by i individually (i.e., first-order effects) or in conjunction with the remaining random inputs (i.e., total-order effects) into two multi-index sets: $\mathcal{Y}_i^F = \{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{T} : s_i \neq 0, s_l = 0 \text{ for } l \neq i\}$ and $\mathcal{Y}_i^T = \{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{T} : s_i \neq 0\}$, where $\mathcal{Y}_i^F \subset \mathcal{T}$ and $\mathcal{Y}_i^T \subset \mathcal{T}$. Given that the PCE coefficients are vector-valued with the dimension equal to the number of the retained diffusion coefficients, i.e., $\eta_{\mathbf{s}} \in \mathbb{R}^g$, the corresponding first-order Sobol' indices for each of g diffusion coordinates are estimated as

$$S_{g,i} = \frac{\sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{Y}_{g,i}^F} \eta_{g,\mathbf{s}}^2 \gamma_{g,\mathbf{s}}}{\sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{Y}_g} \eta_{g,\mathbf{s}}^2 \gamma_{g,\mathbf{s}}}, \quad (8)$$

and the total-order Sobol' indices can be written as

$$S_{T_{g,i}} = \frac{\sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{Y}_{g,i}^T} \eta_{g,\mathbf{s}}^2 \gamma_{g,\mathbf{s}}}{\sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{Y}_g} \eta_{g,\mathbf{s}}^2 \gamma_{g,\mathbf{s}}}, \quad (9)$$

where $\gamma_{\mathbf{s}} = \langle \Phi_{\mathbf{s}}^2 \rangle$ with $\Phi_{\mathbf{s}}$ from Eq. (4). We can combine all first-order sensitivity indices and all total-order sensitivity into respective vectors: $\mathbf{S}_i = (S_{g,i})$ and $\mathbf{S}_{T_i} = (S_{T_{g,i}})$, which are $\in \mathbb{R}^g$ given the dimension of retained diffusion coefficients g .

B.2 Application 1: Lotka-Volterra Dynamical System

The first model considered for applying the global sensitivity analysis (GSA) framework using GDMaps PCE was the classic Lotka-Volterra dynamical system, representing population dynamics resulting from interactions between a prey species and predator species. The model is defined in terms of the system of two coupled, non-linear ordinary differential equations (ODEs):

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{du}{dt} &= \alpha u - \beta uv, \\ \frac{dv}{dt} &= \delta uv - \gamma v,\end{aligned}\tag{10}$$

where u is the prey population, v is the predator population, and $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta$ are stochastic model parameters described in Tab. 1.

GSA was first applied to the Lotka-Volterra model as in Eq. (10) with two stochastic parameters following an example from Kontolati et al.²[5]. The initial conditions for prey and predator populations were $u(t=0) = 10$ and $v(t=0) = 5$, respectively; the distributions of uncertain parameters (α and β) followed Tab. 1 and γ and δ were fixed to $\gamma = 1.50$ and $\delta = 0.75$. The accuracy of the surrogate model using GDMaps PCE was tested by Kontolati et al. [5] through out-of-sample reconstruction, which ensured that GSA applied on the surrogate would also result in accurate estimates. Following the best-performing sample size from the reference example, $\mathcal{N} = 600$ samples $\mathcal{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{N} \times 2}$ were randomly generated. As in the reference, for each combination of two parameters in the sample, the system was solved using time period T set to 25 and discretised in $n = 512$ points. The output was a $\mathcal{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{N} \times 1024}$ matrix, where solutions $\{u(t), v(t)\}$ for each corresponding sample were concatenated into a single vector. Each of the 600 solutions was reshaped to a square matrix $\{\mathbf{Y}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{32 \times 32}\}_{i=1}^{\mathcal{N}=600}$. Performing GDMaps with a constant value of $p = 10$ yielded orthonormal matrices on the Grassmannian $\{\mathbf{U}_i, \mathbf{V}_i \in \mathcal{G}_{(10,32)}\}_{i=1}^{\mathcal{N}=600}$. We preserved three parsimoniously selected diffusion coordinates ($g = 3$) and employed a PCE surrogate that utilised a total-degree basis with a maximal polynomial degree of $s_{\max} = 6$, resulting in 28 polynomials in the PCE basis. To calculate the first- and total-order sensitivity indices, we resampled the parameters fifty times and averaged the resulting GSA estimates over the repeated surrogates.

Table 1. Details of the uncertain input parameters for the Lotka-Volterra dynamical system.

Variable	Distribution	Description
α	$\sim \mathcal{U}(0.90, 1.05)$	Natural growth rate of prey in the absence of predation
β	$\sim \mathcal{U}(0.10, 0.18)$	Death rate per encounter of prey due to predation
γ	$\sim \mathcal{U}(8, 18)$	Natural death rate of predators in the absence of prey
δ	$\sim \mathcal{U}(8, 18)$	Reproduction rate of predators per prey eaten

Next, the GSA framework using GDMaps PCE was employed for the Lotka-Volterra model with four stochastic parameters, as presented in Tab. 1. Instead of generating 600 random samples and resampling the parameter space fifty times, Saltelli’s extension for generating low-discrepancy (Sobol’) sequences was utilised with 1024 distinct samples, resulting in the total sample size of $\mathcal{N} = 6144$; thus, the input matrix $\mathcal{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{6144 \times 4}$ was obtained. The rest of the setup is identical to the previous example with two stochastic parameters, the only difference being that the maximal polynomial degree of $s_{\max} = 10$ was applied, resulting in 1001 polynomials in the PCE basis, and that first- and total-order sensitivity indices were derived without averaging over results obtained from the resampled input matrices. We contrasted the proposed GSA method with the conventional calculation of Sobol’ sensitivity indices by obtaining the first and total order indices separately for two model outputs, u and v , for fifteen evenly spaced time steps for both setups.

B.3 Application 2: DeepABM-COVID

The second model used to test the GSA method employing GDMaps PCE was DeepABM-COVID. Using the DeepABM framework, this model leverages the concepts of tensor-based calculus and graph neural networks to efficiently execute ABMs on GPU architectures and scale them to population-representative

² Note that the distributions of parameters in the paper differ slightly from those in the accompanying code. The distribution ranges used in this study follow those used in the code.

sizes [2]. The efficiency and speed of simulations for a large-scale spatial model were the main reasons for choosing the DeepABM framework for evaluating the GSA using GDMaps PCE. In the framework, agents are represented not as objects but as agent states organised as tensors. Interactions between agents are expressed as permutation-invariant message-passing processes in graph neural networks. Utilising this framework, DeepABM-COVID simulates COVID-19 spread and transmission dynamics across a default of 100,000 agents for 180 time steps. Additional settings enable researchers to investigate the influence of various interventions such as quarantine, exposure notification, testing, and vaccination. For testing the proposed GSA framework, however, all intervention strategies were excluded from simulations to reduce the number of uncertain parameters. Thus, the model components related to the interventions are not discussed here.

All agent states are comprised of static and dynamic components in the model. As the name suggests, the static component stays unchanged throughout a simulation while affecting an agent’s interactions with other agents. Agents’ static components incorporate the following categorical variables: 1) age, 2) occupation, 3) household, and 4) the number of daily interactions. Each agent is initialised with these attributes based on real-world census data (for attributes 1-3) and mobility data (for attribute 4) specific to King’s County in the State of Washington. Excluding the model elements corresponding to intervention strategies, the dynamic component changing over time and influencing model events incorporates the current disease stage, which at any step takes one of the defined eleven values: “susceptible”, “asymptomatic”, “presymptomatic mild”, “presymptomatic severe”, “mild-symptomatic”, “severe symptomatic”, “hospitalised”, “critical in ICU”, “death”, “hospitalised recovering”, “recovered”.

In each interaction, the transmission of the pathogen in DeepABM-COVID is modelled as follows:

$$P(t, s_i, a_s, n) = 1 - e^{-\lambda(t, s_i, a_s, n)}, \quad (11)$$

where λ -function in the exponent is defined as:

$$\lambda(t, s_i, a_s, n) = \frac{R S_{a_s} A_{s_i} B_n}{\bar{I}} \int_{t-1}^t f_{\Gamma}(u; \mu_i, \sigma_i^2) du. \quad (12)$$

In the expressions above, t is the time elapsed since infection; s_i denotes the symptom status of an infected individual (asymptomatic, mild/severe); a_s indicates the age of the susceptibles; and n is the interaction network type. The following parameters influence the viral transmission: R , a scalar for the overall infection rate using the simplified assumptions that it is the mean number of individuals infected by a mildly/severely symptomatic person; S_{a_s} , the scale-factor for the age of the susceptible under the assumption that some age groups are more susceptible to the pathogen than others; A_{s_i} , the scalar for an infected individual being asymptomatic; B_n , the scale-factor for the interaction network accounting for the duration of interaction; \bar{I} , the mean number of daily interactions (see static parameters), and $f_{\Gamma}(u; \mu_i, \sigma_i^2)$, the PDF of a gamma distribution corresponding to the duration of infectiousness. Accordingly, the rate of infection transmission depends on 1) the infectiousness of the pathogen, 2) the age-dependent susceptibility level, 3) the age-dependent level of being asymptomatic, and 4) the type of interaction network (household, occupation, or random) on which interaction occurred. Another essential attribute is the period of infectiousness modelled with a gamma distribution.

For DeepABM [2], most simulation parameters follow the values referenced in its CPU-driven predecessor, OpenABM [1]. For the second and third components, age is stratified into nine groups: 0-10, 11-20, 21-30, 31-40, 41-50, 51-60, 61-70, 71-80, and 80+. The susceptibility scalars S_{a_s} for the nine age groups are 0.35, 0.69, 1.03, 1.03, 1.03, 1.03, 1.27, 1.52, 1.52, while the scale factors for the infector being asymptomatic A_{s_i} are for the corresponding age groups are 0.0, 0.33, 0.05, 0.05, 0.72, 1.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0. The scale factors for interaction duration B_n are 2, 1, and 0.25 for household, occupation, and random networks, respectively. In gamma distribution accounting for infectiousness duration, μ_i, σ_i^2 are 5.5 and 2.14, respectively. Agent distributions (static parameters) and interactions (attributes of interaction networks) are parameterised using census data.

We considered five uncertain parameters for GSA, described in Tab. 2. While the first parameter directly corresponds to R in the model and thus did not undergo any transformations, the other four parameters followed a simple transformation from the corresponding parameters in Eq. (12): multiplication of all values for S_{a_s} , A_{s_i} , B_n and both μ_i, σ_i^2 in $f_{\Gamma}(u; \mu_i, \sigma_i^2)$ by respective general scale-factors (Tab. 2). In particular, the entire tensors S_{a_s} and A_{s_i} used in DeepABM-COVID were multiplied by S_F and A_F , respectively. The mean range for R was taken from Park et al. [6]. The scalar range for μ, σ^2 in gamma distribution was considered to be close to published estimates [4]. For S_F , A_F and B_F , the ranges were selected to give a mean of one for corresponding uniform distributions. Using low-discrepancy

sequences and the Saltelli sampling method, we generated $\mathcal{N} = 7168$ samples $\mathcal{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{N} \times 5}$ (corresponding to 1024 distinct samples used in the Saltelli sampling algorithm). For each input matrix row, we ran twenty replications, each with the default 180 time steps and 100,000 agents. Networks and agent identities (static model components) were initialised once prior to all simulations. All model runs were performed on GPUs leveraging the computational capability of SURF (Samenwerkende Universitaire RekenFaciliteiten) research services and the Dutch National Supercomputer Snellius.

Table 2. Details of the uncertain input parameters for the DeepABM-COVID model.

Variable	Distribution	Description
R	$\sim \mathcal{U}(1.9, 6.5)$	Multiplicative scalar for overall infection rate
S_F	$\sim \mathcal{U}(0.5, 1.5)$	General multiplicative scalar for susceptibility
A_F	$\sim \mathcal{U}(0.5, 1.5)$	General multiplicative scalar for an infector being asymptomatic
B_F	$\sim \mathcal{U}(0.7, 1.3)$	General multiplicative scalar for interaction duration
Γ_F	$\sim \mathcal{U}(0.7, 1.3)$	General multiplicative scalar for μ, σ^2 in gamma distribution

For conventional GSA, the following five responses were considered in terms of the number of individuals described by a particular state at each time step: “susceptible”, “hospitalised”, “dead”, “recovered”, and “active”. Sobol’ indices were calculated at multiple time steps for each response and averaged over twenty replications. For the proposed GSA framework, the same five solutions used for the conventional GSA were concatenated into a single vector, resulting in an output matrix $\mathcal{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{7168 \times 900}$ for each of the twenty runs. Each of the 7168 solutions in each run was reshaped into a square matrix $\{\mathbf{Y}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{30 \times 30}\}_{i=1}^{\mathcal{N}=7168}$. For GDMaps, we examined multiple values for p and compared the resulting Sobol’ indices across them. We preserved three diffusion coordinates ($g = 3$) and investigated the differences between parsimoniously selected diffusion coordinates and those corresponding to the three largest non-trivial eigenvalues (non-parsimonious implementation). We explored four distinct values for the maximal polynomial degree of s_{\max} in constructing the total-degree PCE basis and compared the respective validation errors and how the resulting first and total order sensitivity indices changed with larger s_{\max} .

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C Results Supplement

C.1 Application 1: Lotka-Volterra Dynamical System

Fig. C.1. Time series of $\mathcal{N} = 600$ realisations of the Lotka-Volterra model with two uncertain parameters $\alpha \sim \mathcal{U}(0.90, 1.05)$ and $\beta \sim \mathcal{U}(0.10, 0.18)$ as inputs randomly sampled from respective distributions. The model outputs for the defined parameter ranges for α and β exhibit oscillatory behaviour.

Fig. C.2. 2D plots of three diffusion coordinates from GDMaps on the Lotka-Volterra model solution using two uncertain parameters α and β (see Tab. 1) as input and $\mathcal{N} = 600$ training samples, using the dimension of the Grassmannian $p = 6$. Diffusion coordinates converged to $\Theta_i = \{\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_5\}$ for parsimonious representation. The colour maps are defined by θ_1 (a, b) and θ_2 (c).

Fig. C.3. Estimates of first- and total-order sensitivity indices of four input parameters (see Tab. 1) for prey (u) and predator (v) populations calculated using (a-d) conventional methods at fifteen evenly spaced time steps with 95% bootstrap confidence intervals and (e, f) GSA via GDMaps PCE. For the traditional GSA method, sample size $n = 1024$ with $n(d + 2) = 6144$ parameter sets for Saltelli's Sobol' sequences were used. For GSA via GDMaps PCE, $\mathcal{N} = 6144$, Grassmann manifold dimension $p = 10$, and maximal polynomial degree $s_{\max} = 10$. Total effects surpass main effects, especially for predator population v , and individual parameter contributions explain little of the output variance in (a-d). Main effect indices decrease while total-effect indices rise over time in (c-d). Negative indices in (a, c) may be due to inadequate sample size. α contributes least to output variance in (a, b, d). Interaction effects on output variance are significantly larger than main effects for all parameters in (e, f), with α having the lowest total-order indices and γ having the largest contributions to the variance in terms of both main and total effects. (g-i) 2D plots of selected diffusion coordinates ($\Theta_i = \theta_1, \theta_3, \theta_2$) for Sobol' indices in (e, f).

C.2 Application 2: DeepABM-COVID

Fig. C.4. Estimates of first- and total-order sensitivity indices for five input parameters (see Tab. 2) across five model outputs using Sobol' indices at six evenly spaced time steps, averaged over twenty runs. Error bars represent 95% bootstrap confidence intervals. Comparable patterns are observed for “susceptible”, “death”, and “recovered”, as well as “hospitalized” and “active” due to their direct relationships. For “hospitalised” and “active”, most of the variance in the model output is caused by interaction effects, while “susceptible”, “death,” and “recovered” show higher main effect indices for R , A_F , and S_F . B_F and Γ_F exhibit the smallest estimates of S_i and S_{T_i} for “susceptible”, “death”, and “recovered” and of S_{T_i} for “hospitalized” and “active” outputs.

Fig. C.5. 2D plots illustrating the first three non-trivial diffusion coordinates (non-parsimonious representation) from GDMaps applied to the DeepABM-COVID model output for run 16, utilising six distinct Grassmannian dimensions $p = \{3, 13, 17, 22, 23, 24\}$. Colour maps are determined by the diffusion coordinates on the x -axis. Lower Grassmannian dimensions are associated with slower timescales discovered by DMaps, as evidenced by the axes' scales. Comparisons within columns reveal that the resulting structures exhibit similarities, such as in pairs (j, p), (e, h), and (l, r), or appear as rotated versions with varying scales, as demonstrated by pairs (d, g), (k, n), and (l, o).

Fig. C.6. 2D plots of three diffusion coordinates from GDMaps applied to the DeepABM-COVID model output for run 16, employing a parsimonious representation and six distinct Grassmannian dimensions $p = \{3, 13, 17, 22, 23, 24\}$. Colour maps are determined by the diffusion coordinates on the x -axis. As the Grassmannian dimension p increases, the method more frequently selects diffusion coordinates with lower corresponding eigenvalues (higher subscript values) compared to smaller p values, as evident in the left column. The resulting structures exhibit similarities, as demonstrated by the subplots (e, g, h, k, j, m, p, q).

Fig. C.7. Distributions of parsimoniously selected diffusion coordinates for the Grassmannian dimension $p = 17$ obtained from eight distinct runs: $\{1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15\}$ of the DeepABM-COVID model with resulting output $\mathcal{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{7168 \times 900}$. Higher subscript values correspond to lower non-trivial eigenvalues λ_i , ordered from high to low. The distributions of diffusion coordinates associated with higher eigenvalues exhibit multimodal characteristics, while those corresponding to lower eigenvalues display unimodal and even Gaussian-like features.

Fig. C.8. Distributions of parsimoniously selected diffusion coordinates for the Grassmannian dimension $p = 24$ from eight distinct runs: $\{1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15\}$ of the DeepABM-COVID model with resulting output $\mathcal{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{7168 \times 900}$. The distributions of diffusion coordinates with smaller subscripts (associated with higher eigenvalues) are multimodal, whereas those corresponding to lower eigenvalues are unimodal and even Gaussian-like.

Fig. C.9. Mean estimates of first-order sensitivity indices for five uncertain input parameters and five aggregated output measures from the DeepABM-COVID model, acquired using the GSA framework with GDMaps and PCE. Four varying maximal polynomial degrees $s_{\max} = \{10, 15, 20, 25\}$ and six distinct Grassmannian dimensions $p = \{3, 13, 17, 22, 23, 24\}$ were employed. Lower s_{\max} values result in increased first-order sensitivity indices, which is particularly evident for the first diffusion coordinates and smaller Grassmannian dimensions p .

Fig. C.10. Mean estimates of total-order sensitivity indices for five uncertain input parameters and five aggregated output measures from the DeepABM-COVID model, obtained with GSA framework using GDMaps PCE for four varying maximal polynomial degrees $s_{\max} = \{10, 15, 20, 25\}$ and six distinct Grassmannian dimensions $p = \{3, 13, 17, 22, 23, 24\}$. With increasing s_{\max} , the accuracy of model output reconstruction improves (thereby reducing validation error), resulting in higher total-order sensitivity indices for all parameters and Grassmannian dimensions p . The only deviation from this trend pertains to s_{\max} , which corresponds with the mean validation errors illustrated in Fig. 4 of the main text.